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Anowar's Handbook on Textile Raw Materials I

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for textile engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of textile engineering and textile fibre. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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Textile Raw Materials: of

Cotton fibre : Define fibre : Fibres are hair-like substances which consists fibrous structure and length is thousand times higher than its width, is called fibre.

Define textile fibre : The materials which consists fibrous structure and length is thousand times higher than its width/diameter and can be spun into yarn, suitable for weaving or knitting and easily colored by suitable dyes are called textile fibre.

What are the major characteristics of textile fibre?

- 1) Fibrous structure
- 2) length is thousand times higher than width/diameter
- 3) Enables fibres to be twisted together to form yarn
- 4) Sufficient strength
- 5) Elasticity & Flexibility
- 6) Fineness
- 7) Affinity to dye

Classify fibre on the basis of natural fibre.

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Briefly discuss the properties of Textile fibre.

Physical properties:

Length: staple length can be three types such as short (2''), medium (2-4') and long (>4') which affects strength, processing, appearance etc.

Strength: The capability of a fibre to support a load is known as its strength. Tenacity = strength / linear

density: It is expressed by N/Tex.

Flexibility: is that property to resist repeated bending and folding.

Cohesiveness: It is the ability of the fibre to cling (মোড়ানকা) together.

Fineness: Fineness describes the quality of a fibre i.e how fine a fibre is. It is expressed by the terms count tex, denier.

Crump: indicates waves or bends along the length of the fibre.

Elasticity: is the power of recovery from deformation.

Resiliency: Ability of a fibre to spring back to its original position after folding, creasing or deformation.

Density: indicates the mass per unit volume.

Chemical properties:

Absorbency: is the ability of fibre to take up moisture.

Moisture Regain: The ratio of wt. of water in the material to the oven dry wt. of the material is called moisture regain. It is denoted by R.

Moisture Regain, $R = \frac{W}{D} \times 100$ where, wt. of water in material = W, oven dry wt. of material = D.

Moisture content: The ratio of water in a material to the total wt. of the material is called moisture content. It is denoted by c.

Moisture content, $c = \frac{W}{W+D} \times 100$
Acid, Alkali, heat \uparrow should carefully choose for textile fibre.
Textile fibre can be affected by Acid, Alkali, heat, water.

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**** "All fibres are not textile fibres" - explain from your understanding**

Textile fibres should have length, strength, flexibility, cohesiveness, fineness, crimp, elasticity, absorbency and power to react with acid and alkali and power to protect the effect of biological agents etc. Suppose,

cotton and jute fibres have the above qualities and considered as textile fibres. But fibres of banana tree only fibre, not textile fibre as they do not show qualities like elasticity, strength, appearance etc.

**** Differentiate staple fibre and filament.**

Staple fibre	Filament
01. Staple fibres are natural fibre.	01. Filaments are manmade fibre (except silk)
02. Staple fibres are mainly shorter in length, controlled by nature	02. Filaments are continuous in length, controlled by manufacturer.
03. Staple fibres are directly used in spinning & weaving	03. Filaments are cut in shorter length as per requirements.
04. Staple fibres contain impurities like dust, leaves, dirt etc.	04. Filament doesn't contain impurities such as dust, leaves etc.
05. Apparel made from staple is not and comfortable.	05. Apparel made from staple is not not and comfortable.

How manmade fibre is using more than natural fibre?
How natural fibre is replacing by manmade fibre?

- 1) The strength of MMF is greater than NF 2) The production of NF depends on nature but for MMF there is no dependence.
- 3) MMF is cheaper than NF 4) The properties of manmade fibre can be changed but not so in case of NF.

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Why stronger yarn can be produced from finer fibre.
Yarn made by finer fibre has more fibres in cross section.

Differentiate Natural fibre and Manmade fibre

NF	MME
01. The NF are those which are provided by nature like plant, animals, etc.	01. The fibres made by synthetic or regenerating system.
02. No. of molecules are not limited, controlled by nature.	02. No. of molecules are limited, controlled by man.
03. The fabric made from natural fibre is comfortable and good for health.	03. The fabric made from MME is uncomfortable and not good for health.
04. NF is expensive because its production cost is high.	04. MME is not expensive because its production cost is not so high.
05. Example: Cotton, Jute, Flax etc.	05. Example: Nylon, Polyester, Lycra etc.

Compare between Hydrophilic and Hydrophobic fibre

Hydrophilic	Hydrophobic
01. The fibre, which has more affinity for water that means more absorbency, is called hydrophilic.	01. The fibre which has less affinity for water that means less absorbency than hydrophilic is called hydrophobic.
02. More Amorphous	02. More Crystalline
03. Example: Cotton, Wool, Silk	03. Example: Nylon, Polyester.
04. Dyeing can be done easily	04. Difficult to dye.
05.	

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Botanical Name of cotton fibre?

- 01) *Gossypium hirsutum*
- 02) *Gossypium herbaceum*

Producing country of cotton fibre:

USA, China, India, Russia, Egypt, Brazil
[Egypt → country linking northeast Africa and middle east]

Cultivation of cotton fibre:

- 01) seed planted
- 02) Two weeks later, two leaves appears on the plant
- 03) At five or six weeks later, the first flower appears
- 04) At eight to nine weeks, the first flower blooms
- 05) Flowers fall off leaving boll
- 06) Seed hairs starts to grow inside the bolls
- 07) For 16-18 days, fibre length and perimeter achieved
- 08) For the next 22-50 days, cellulose is deposited inside the fibres
- 09) When cellulose deposition stops, the bolls dry and cracks to open
- 10) These bolls are picked up manually or by machine

Ginning: The process involves to separate the cotton fibres from seeds is called ginning.

objects of Ginning: 01. To separate fibres fully from its seeds. 02. To collect seeds and waste together. 03. To collect fibre without any faults. 04. To separate whole fibre.

Difference between Saw gin and Roller gin:

Saw Ginning	Roller Ginning
01. The saw ginning is used mainly for short and medium length cotton.	01. The roller ginning is used for longer length of fibre.
02. The main functional parts of saw ginning are disk of saw teeth and grid bars (through which dirt and extraneous matter pass).	02. The main functional part of roller ginning is spiked rollers.

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Lint: The fibres, which are found after first ginning and used for producing yarn, fabric etc.

Lintern: The fibres which are found after second ginning and used for producing pure cellulose.

Chemical composition of cotton fibre:

- 01) Cellulose: 85-85.5%
- 02) Oil and wax: 0.5%
- 03) Protein and coloring matter: 4.5-5%
- 04) Mineral Matter: 1%
- 05) Moisture: 8.5%

Physical Properties of cotton fibre:

- 01) Specific gravity: 1.54
- 02) Moisture content: 8.5%
- 03) Strength: Tenacity: dry: 3.5 g/d [24-27 cN/Tex] / 1.45 N/Tex wet = dry x 1.1
- 04) Breaking extension: 5-7%
- 05) Resiliency: low
- 06) Abrasion resistance: medium

Chemical properties of cotton fibre:

- 01. Effect of Bleach: All kinds of bleaching agents have its action on cotton. Such as: H₂O₂, NaOCl
- 02. Effect of Acid: Cotton is weakened and destroyed by the effect of Acid. Cotton dissolves fully in conc. of 75% above H₂SO₄
- 03. Effect of Alkali: NaOH shows mercerizing effect and under tension, it increases strength and dye ability.
- 04. Effect of heat: Normally ironing temp. 150°C

Polymer structure/chemical structure of cotton fibre

What is the technical points of increasing strength of cotton fibre for wetting

Water molecules penetration into the amorphous region → Hydrogen bonds with free cellulose hydroxyl groups → Swelling the secondary cell → cements the cellulose chains and fibril together by hydrogen bonding.

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Schematic structure of cotton fibre

$S_1 = 20-35^\circ$
 $S_2 = 26-36^\circ$
 $S_3 = 0^\circ$

Beneath the primary cell wall, the fibrils of secondary wall spiral at about S_1, S_2 .

Classification of cotton on the basis of maturity:

Fig: Mature fibre
 Convolution: Under microscope, matured fibre look like twisted ribbon
 lumen: The hollow canal running the length of the fibre is called lumen.
 Fig: Immature fibre
 Fig: Dead fibre (used in dyeing due to their minimum absorption of dyes and chemicals)

Faults of cotton fibre: Nep, coils, fibre string
Impurities of cotton fibre: Trash, Dust, Crushed seed
 cool & hot weather, shirt, trousers.
End uses: Garments & household fabric such as towels, table cloth, bed sheet, curtains, canvas, sail cloth etc.

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Recent Development of cotton: Naturally colored cotton is developed by gene trans-plantation. Crossing the genes from wild cotton varieties with the cultivated white ones develop this colored cotton. The research is being conducted at the university of agricultural sciences (UAS), Dharwad Karnataka India, to promote the cultivation of natural colored cotton. The colors that have been developed are white, orange, Red, Yellow, Green, purple, Brown, Blue and Black.

Object: An Environment friendly.

[Faint handwritten notes and diagrams on the reverse side of the page, including a diagram of a cylindrical object with internal components.]

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Jute fibre

Botanical Names of Jute fibre: 1) Corchorus capsularis
2) Corchorus olitorius

Why jute is called bast fibre or Retinae bast fibre?

Fibres which are obtained from stem, bark or leaf of certain vegetable plants are called bast fibres. Such as: jute, Flax, Hemp, ramie, Kenaf etc.

Define retting: Retting is the process by which the fibre is removed from the stalk where barks are loosened & separated from the woody stalk due to the removal of pectin, gums etc.

Chemical composition of jute fibre:

- 01) Cellulose - 65.2%
- 02) Hemicellulose - 22.2%
- 03) Lignin - 10.8%
- 04) Water soluble materials - 1.5%
- 05) Fat and wax - 0.3%

Draw the structure of Lignin & define

Lignin is a adhesive mtl which linkages with cellulose & increases strength, ductility, flexibility and extension. It is responsible for wide range of color range.

Difference between cellulose and hemicellulose

Cellulose	Hemicellulose
1) 7,000-15,000 Glucose unit	1) 500-3000 sugar units
2) Unbranched Polymer	2) Branched Polymer
3) Crystalline structure	3) Amorphous structure
4) Textile, Paper	4) Films and gels in packaging.

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Physical properties of jute :

- 01. Specific gravity: 1.48
- 02. Moisture regain: 13.75%
- 03. Tenacity: 3.5 g/d (dry), But in wet condition lower than dry
- 04. Resiliency: Bad
- 05. Abrasion resistance: Moderate
- 06. Dimensional stability: Good.

Chemical properties of jute:

Effect of bleaching; Not affected by oxidising or reducing agent.

Effect of Acid and Alkali: Easily damaged by hot dilute or cold concentrated acids.

Effect of organic solvents: Resistant to organic solvents.

Effect of heat: Burns rapidly

End uses:

- 01. Packaging textiles
 - 02. Geotextiles
 - 03. Agro textiles
 - 04. Jute reinforced Composite in build tech and mobiltech
 - 05. Coated textile
 - 06. Protective textile
 - 07. Home textiles.
- Mobiltech → Prefabricated building
mobile → able to move

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Flax Fibre / Linen fibre

Botanical Name: *Linum unilatiatum*

Producing country: Rumia, Belgium, Holland, England

Ireland, USA, Canada, Argentina

Linseed oil

The seeds of flax plant, which are the source of linseed oil and linseed cake.

Procedure of flax fibre collection:

Rippling → Combing to remove seed & leaf

↓
Retting

- a) Dew-retting
 - b) water retting
 - c) chemical retting
- NaOH

↓
washing & Drying

↓
Breaking: Flax fibre passed into fluted roller & breaking the stalks (m pipe)

↓
Scutching: Removed broken stalks

↓
Hackling: combing of fibre for making straight

Chemical composition:

01) Cellulose: 63% 02) Fat: 1.08% 03) Water: 11.63%

04) Gum + wax: 2.1% 05) Ash: 0.63%

Pectin: A soluble gelatinous Polysaccharide which yields a gel.

Ash: Mineral rich residue.

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Physical properties:

- 01) specific gravity: 1.54
- 02) Moisture Regain: 12%
- 03) strength: 5.8 g/d (dry) and wet strength is higher than dry.
- 04) Elongation: 1.8% (dry) and 2.2% (wet).
- 05) Avg length 45-60cm
- 06) Abrasion resistance: moderate.

Chemical properties:

Effect of bleach: Flax is more difficult to bleach than cotton.

Effect of Acid: It is attacked by hot diluted acid and cold concentrated acid

Effect of Alkali: Flax has a good resistance to alkaline solution

- End uses:
- 01) clothings
 - 02) Table cloth, Napkin, Towel, bed cover
 - 03) Sewing thread
 - 04) Suture thread
 - 05) Banknote & cigarette paper
 - 06) Blending with cotton.

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Hemp fibre :

Botanical Name: Cannabis sativa

Producing country: China, Italy, India, Switzerland, France etc.

Physical properties of Hemp:

- 01. Specific gravity : 1.48
- 02. M.R. : 12%
- 03. length : 40-80 inch
- 04. Fineness is less than linen but tensile strength is higher
- 05. Lumen broader than flax and pines

Ramie fibre :

Botanical Name : Boehmeria

Producing country : Japan, Germany, France, China etc.

Properties :

- 01) Tenacity : 6.7 (dry), 8.7 g/d (wet)
- 02) length of fibre : 45 cm
- 03) Narrow lumen and tends to have hairy feel
- 04) Fibre is white and lustrous

End uses : 1) Shirting 2) Table cloth 3) Napkin 4) upholstery and furnishing fabrics 5) Fishing net 6) Sewing thread.

Sisal (leaf fibre) :

Botanical Name : Agave sisalana

Producing country : America, Africa, India, Florida etc.

Physical properties :

- 01. Tenacity : 4.4
- 02) M.R. : 8%
- 03) B. extension : 2%
- 04) Lignin : 6%
- 05) Avg. length : 2.5 mm.

End uses : Cordage and Blending; Marine ropes, Sacks, Paper filter

Coir (Fruit fibre) : obtained from the coconut and the fibrous mass between the outer cell and the actual nut.

Properties : 01) Wrinkle resistant due to high degree of stiffness
02) Strong and Resistant abrasive wear

End uses : Matting and cordages

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Wool & wool fibre (sheep, goat, camel etc)

Producing countries: Argentina, Australia, Britain, Holland, Spain, Germany, New Zealand, South Africa, France, Canada, USA, Pakistan, Iran etc.

Preparatory process of wool fibre:

- Sorting and Grading: is done according to fineness, length and strength of fibre.
- Scouring: washing and warm soapy water to remove the natural grease or gum, dirt and dust.
- Drying: removed water by using warm air.
- Oiling: wool fibre is treated by various oil including animal, vegetable and mineral.

Physical properties:

- 01) Tenacity: 1-1.7 g/d (dry) and 8-1.6 g/d (wet)
- 02) Elongation at Break: 25-35% under standard condition and 25-50% in wet condition
- 03) Specific gravity: 1.32
(Example: $\frac{\rho_{sample}}{\rho_{H_2O}}$ = specific gravity relative density)
- 04) Hygroscopic and Hydrophilic fibre. 05) Resiliency: Excellent
(abstracting moisture from the air)
- 06) M.R: 13-16%
07. L = 2-8%

Chemical properties:

- Effect of Acid: Decomposes completely by hot concentrated H_2SO_4
- Effect of Alkali: Dissolve in high concentrated NaOH
- Effect of organic solvents: Good resistant to dry cleaning and other common solvents
- Effect of microorganism: Poor resistant to mildew and bacteria.

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Composition of wool:

- Keratin → 33%
- Dirty → 26%
- Suint → 28%
- Fat → 12%
- Mineral matters → 1%

Composition of Keratin:

- Carbon → 50%
- Oxygen → 10%
- Hydrogen → 12%
- Nitrogen → 25%
- Sulfur → 3%

Suint: A natural greasy substance in sheep's wool

Dust: Trash → above 500µm, Fine Dust → 50-500µm, Microdust → 15-50µm.

Why wool fibre is used for ^{winter} warm-weather clothing / ^{cool} hot weather clothing

With high temperature wool fibre interlocked with one another. (setting property)
So wool fibre provide warm nature.

Differentiate the terms of woollen and worsted

woollen	worsted
01. Short length fibre	01. High length fibre
02. Weak fibre	02. Stronger fibre
03. Softer	03. Harsher

End uses: Dressing material, Blankets, Carpets, jackets etc.

↘ **Grainnetting:** Recycled waste wool fibres are obtained by separately reducing the unbrined materials to a fibrous mass by a picking and shredding process called grain netting.

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Silk fibre

Producing countries: China, Japan, India, Italy, Spain, France, Brazil etc.

Composition of silk:

- Gum or sericin: 22-25%
- Fibroin: 62.5-67%
- Water (moisture): 10-11%
- Salts: 1-1.5%

Composition of Fibroin:

- Glycine: 38%
- Alanine: 22%
- Serine: 16%
- Tyrosine: 9%
- Other Amino Acid: 16%

Physical properties of silk:

- 1) Tenacity: 3.5-5 g/d (dry) and wet strength in 75-85% of dry
- 2) Specific gravity: 1.25
- 3) Elongation at Break: 20-25%
- 4) M.R: 11%
- 5) Resiliency: Good
- 6) Abrasion resistance: good

Chemical properties of silk:

Effect of Acids: silk is dissolved in strong mineral acids. Ex: HNO₃ will create yellow colored effect on silk.

Effect of Alkali: dissolved in high concentrated NaOH

Effect of bleach: silk fibroin is attacked by oxidising agent, so H₂O₂ should be used with care.

Manufacturing steps of silk:

Sericulture → Sorting cocoons → Softening the sericin → Reeling → Throwing

Sericulture: The cocoon production process from silk

worms is called sericulture. Sorting cocoons: The cocoons

Life cycle of silk worms:

are sorted according to color, size, shape and texture.

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Softening the sericin: Cocoons are put through a series of hot and cold immersions as the sericine must be softened to permit the unwinding of the filament as one continuous thread.

Reeling: The process of filament collection from cocoons is called reeling.

Throwing: The production of yarn from reeled silk, known as throwing, involves ^{under twisting} twisting.

Degumming: In order to make silk fabric soft and glossy, it is necessary to remove the sericine or gum by a treatment called degumming.

Recipe: soap: 5-75% (on the wt. of silk)

Silk: water: 1:14

Temp: 95°C

Time: 30 min

pH: 10

End uses: woven and knitted goods in a wide variety of fabrics, curtain, silk shawls & other ladies wear.

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